

ProofCloud: A Proof Retrieval Engine for Verified Proofs in Higher Order Logic

Shuai Wang*

INRIA Rocquencourt, Paris, France

ILLIC, University of Amsterdam, The Netherlands

shuai.wang@student.uva.nl

ProofCloud is a proof retrieval engine for verified proofs in higher order logic. It provides a fast proof searching service for mathematicians and computer scientists for the reuse of proofs and proof packages. In addition, it includes the first complete proof checking results and benchmarks of the OpenTheory repository.

1 Introduction

Interactive Theorem Provers (ITPs) have been playing an important role in formal mathematics, software verification and hardware verification. In recent years, there has been dramatic progress in the usability and power of ITPs. Among them, theorem provers in the HOL family are among the most widely used in this domain. The HOL family consists of HOL Light [5], HOL4 [10] and ProofPower [8], to name a few. These ITPs implement the same higher order logic, namely Church’s simple type theory [6]. However, they each contain significant theory formalisations that are not accessible to each other. HOL Light [5] has a formalisation of complex analysis while HOL4 has a formalisation of probability theory [10]. In contrast, ProofPower has a formalization of the Z specification language [8]. These ITPs were developed without considering proof sharing and reuse to avoid repeated work proving large theorems. Moreover, ITPs may not be bug-free and may lead to errors in generated proofs which are not necessarily apparent within the proof systems themselves. Additionally, proofs can be huge, making them difficult or even impossible to be checked by hand (e.g. the Kepler Conjecture [4]). The demand of reliability of such systems leads to the necessity of proof checking, especially methods and tools independent from the ITPs involved. All this requires theorem provers to export proofs in a certain format. OpenTheory is a format and a proof repository for the HOL family with this purpose. Taking advantage of the similarity of the logic and design between these systems, OpenTheory [6] has developed a standard format for serializing proofs and sharing proofs [6]. ITPs in the HOL family can export proofs to the OpenTheory format as article files (packages of proofs and relevant information). These files are then converted to Dedukti [9] format by a proof translator, namely Holide [1], for the sake of proof checking.

HOL Light [5] is an open source interactive theorem prover for higher order logic. Its logic is an extension of Church’s simple type theory with polymorphic type [5]. Higher order logic is also known as simple type theory. It is a logic on top of simply typed λ -calculus with additional axioms and inference rules [5]. The type of a term is either an individual, a boolean type or a function type. A term is either a constant, a variable (e.g. x), an abstraction (e.g. $\lambda x.x$) or a well-typed application (e.g. $(\lambda x.x)y$). The

*The author was supported by the MPRI-INRIA scholarship during this project.

notation $x : \iota$ means that the term x is of type ι . Types are sometimes omitted for simplicity of representation. The equality is of polymorphic type and plays three roles in HOL Light: definition, equivalence and bi-implication.

type variables	α, β
type operators	p
types	$A, B ::= \alpha \mid p(A_1, \dots, A_n)$
term variables	x, y
term constants	c
terms	$M, N ::= x \mid \lambda x : A. M \mid MN \mid c$

This paper presents ProofCloud, a proof retrieval engine for retrieval of verified higher order logic proofs and some related proof checking results. This paper is organised as follows: we first introduce OpenTheory and explain its kernel and the recent updates in Section 2. Following that is ProofCloud (Section 3) and the implementation (Section 4). Finally, the evaluation and benchmarks of proof checking are included.

2 OpenTheory

OpenTheory [6] is a cross-platform proof package manager for proofs in ITPs of the HOL family. The standard library of OpenTheory groups theorems into packages, including theorems of booleans, sets, lists, etc. Moreover, it contains a repository of proof packages allowing sharing and reuse of proofs between theorem provers in the HOL family. OpenTheory has inspired further exploration of proof management between HOL families [7] as well as the development of several projects (e.g. [1] and [2]) taking advantage of these packages.

$\frac{}{\vdash t = t}$ refl	$\frac{}{\{\varphi\} \vdash \varphi}$ assume φ	$\frac{\Delta \vdash \varphi \quad \Gamma \vdash \varphi = \psi}{\Gamma \cup \Delta \vdash \psi}$ eqMp
$\frac{\Gamma \vdash t = u}{\Gamma \vdash (\lambda v. t) = (\lambda v. u)}$ absThm v	$\frac{\Gamma \vdash f = g \quad \Delta \vdash x = y}{\Gamma \cup \Delta \vdash fx = gy}$ appThm	
$\frac{\Gamma \vdash \varphi \quad \Delta \vdash \psi}{(\Gamma \setminus \{\psi\}) \cup (\Delta \setminus \{\varphi\}) \vdash \varphi = \psi}$ deductAntisym	$\frac{\Gamma \vdash \varphi}{\Gamma[\sigma] \vdash \varphi[\sigma]}$ subst σ	
$\frac{}{\vdash (\lambda v. t)u = t[u/v]}$ betaConv $((\lambda v. t)u)$	$\frac{}{c = t}$ defineConst t	
$\frac{}{\vdash abs(rep\ a) = a}$	$\frac{\vdash \varphi t \quad \vdash (rep(abs\ r) = r) = \varphi r}{\vdash abs(rep\ a) = a}$ defineTypeOp n abs rep vs	

Table 1: OpenTheory version 5 Logic Kernel

Table 1 illustrates the primitive inference rules of the OpenTheory logic kernel which has some small differences compared with the HOL Light kernel¹. Different from other proof libraries, OpenTheory

¹Note that *appThm* Corresponds to MK_COMB in HOL Light.

was not designed to be a general purpose proof repository. It is a specialised library and format for proof sharing between the ITPs in the HOL family.

3 ProofCloud

ProofCloud² is a proof retrieval engine for easy searching of verified higher order logic proofs. It consists of a presentation of proofs and proof packages, the results of some statistical and structural analyses, together with their proof checking results. So far it has been populated with 1687 proofs from 6 packages of OpenTheory. Information of each proof and package is presented on separate webpages. Taking classical proofs as those using the axiom of choice, ProofCloud can distinguish between classical proofs and constructive proofs. Furthermore, it tracks the origin of classicism, in other words, which classical lemmas³ were used within the proof. With this ability, the amount as well as the percentage of classical proofs of a certain package is calculated and displayed on its (package) page. Users will also find a statistical analysis on the size of proofs and links to proof checking results. As far as the author knows, this is the only online proof retrieval engine of its kind. The specifications of ProofCloud is presented in Appendix A.

Figure 1: The Interface of ProofCloud

²<http://airobert.github.io/proofcloud/>

³To avoid confusion, all theorems used to prove the conclusion are referred to as lemmas when referring to a specific theorem.

4 Implementation

ProofCloud is a customised search engine from Swiftype⁴. It was implemented to provide fast searching service of proofs for mathematicians and computer scientists using ITPs in the HOL family. It has an elegant and user-friendly interface with the search results clearly displayed. It has been on service since July 2015 and just been upgraded to version 2. It contains more than 1700 pages of information about theorems and packages of higher order logic. These pages were generated by extending a modified version of HOL Light⁵ with functions to import and export proof articles and generate proof analysis results in the form of webpages (for example Figure 2). More specifically, proof analysis takes advantage of the proof logging method. Instead of erasing the proof after exporting, it performs proof analysis and generates webpages with a representation of the results.

Figure 2: A Proof Page of ProofCloud

Entry	Value
Name	ALL_F
Conclusion	!! ALL (x. F) I <=> NULL I
Constructive Proof	No
Axiom	!t. t ∨ ~t (\a. a = (\b. (\c. c) = (\c. c))) (\d. (\e. d e) = d)
Classical Lemmas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> !x s. ~(x INSERT s = {}) !t. ~ ~t <=> t !t. (t <=> T) ∨ (t <=> F) !p. (?x. ~p x) <=> ~(!x. p x) !p. ~(!x. p x) <=> (?x. ~p x) !p. ~(?x. p x) <=> (!x. ~p x) !! set_of_list l = {} <=> NULL I !s t. ~(s = t) <=> (?x. x IN t <=> ~(x IN s)) !s. (?x. x IN s) <=> ~(s = {})
Constructive Lemmas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> T !x y s. x IN y INSERT s <=> x = y ∨ x IN s !x y. x = y <=> y = x !x y. x = y ==> y = x !h t. ~NULL (CONS h t) !h t. set_of_list (CONS h t) = h INSERT set_of_list t !x s. ~(x INSERT s = {}) !x s. x INSERT s = {y y = x ∨ y IN s} !x. ~(x IN {})

So far ProofCloud includes six OpenTheory packages in total. These packages are *base* (the standard library with some subpackages), *stream*, *probability*, *natural-bits*, *natural-divides* and *natural-prime*. Other packages will be added in the near future. An analysis of the dependency of packages of OpenTheory is as shown in Figure 3. To load a package, it is required to load all the packages it depends on primarily. In addition, the package *modular* is a parametric theory and requires the *modular-witness* theory which defines a suitable signature. Similarly *gfp* is another parametric theory. These packages are

⁴Swiftype (<https://swiftype.com/>) is a customisable search engine with simple APIs and real-time indexing.

⁵<http://src.gilith.com/hol-light.html>

being updated and therefore not included for now. The package *modular* and *gfp* and packages depending on them will be added to ProofCloud in the near future.

Figure 3: Dependency of Packages of OpenTheory

4.1 Updates of OpenTheory

To obtain the proof checking results for ProofCloud, Holide has to be updated according to the changes of OpenTheory. In version 6⁶, OpenTheory expanded its logic kernel with four inference rules: *proveHyp*, *trans*, *sym* and *defineTypeOp* (as in Table 2) to generate more compact article files (packages of proofs and some relevant information). Following this update, some projects depending on the OpenTheory repository are out of date. Holide (version 1) [1] is one of them⁷.

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \frac{\Gamma \vdash \varphi \quad \Delta \vdash \psi}{\Gamma \cup (\Delta \setminus \{\varphi\}) \vdash \psi} \text{ proveHyp} \\
 \frac{\Gamma \vdash s = t \quad \Delta \vdash t = u}{\Gamma \vdash s = u} \text{ trans} \\
 \frac{\Gamma \cup \Delta \vdash s = u}{\Gamma \vdash \varphi = \psi} \text{ sym} \\
 \frac{\Gamma \vdash \psi = \varphi \quad \vdash \varphi t}{\vdash \text{abs}(repa) = a \quad \vdash \lambda r. \varphi r = (\lambda r. (rep(abs r) = r))} \text{ defineTypeOp n abs rep vs}
 \end{array}$$

Table 2: New and Updated Inference Rules of OpenTheory (version 6)

4.2 Holide, Dedukti and Proof Checking

Dedukti is a logical framework for defining logics and expressing proofs. Cousineau and Dowek proved that Higher Order Logic can be embedded in the $\lambda\Pi$ -calculus Modulo [3]. This resulted in proposing

⁶A full comparison table between version 5 and version 6 is online at <http://www.gilith.com/pipermail/opentheory-users/2014-December/000461.html>

⁷The old Holide (version 1) is at <https://www.rocq.inria.fr/deducteam/Holide/>. The upgraded version is maintained by the author and is available at <http://airobert.github.io/holide/> also as an open-source software.

Dedukti as a proof checker [9]. To transform proofs from the OpenTheory format [6] to the Dedukti format, we need a translator, namely Holide [1]. Holide uses a modular translation of higher order logic to Dedukti, making it possible to extend the translation [1]. Recent updates of the OpenTheory urges an update of the Holide program. The following shows an extension of the bijective translation by adding corresponding translation of the *sym*, *trans* and *proveHyp* inference rules. Moreover, *defineConstList* and *hdTl* are added while processing the proof articles. In addition, the translation of *defineTypeOp* is updated while the commands *version* and *pragma* are omitted during the translation. The translation notations of types, terms and proofs are kept consistent with [1]. On the left are the (OpenTheory) inferences and on the right are the corresponding Dedukti formula. Details of translation are as follows:

$$\left| \frac{\Gamma \vdash \varphi = \psi}{\Gamma \vdash \psi = \varphi} \text{sym} \right| = \text{Sym}|A||\varphi||\psi||D_1|, \text{ where } \varphi \text{ and } \psi \text{ are of type } A \text{ and } D_1 \text{ is the proof of } \varphi = \psi.$$

$$\left| \frac{\Gamma \vdash s = t \quad \Delta \vdash t = u}{\Gamma \cup \Delta \vdash s = u} \text{trans} \right| = \text{Trans}|A||s||t||u||D_1||D_2|, \text{ where } D_1 \text{ is the proof of } s = t \text{ and } D_2 \text{ is the proof of } t = u$$

$$\left| \frac{\Gamma \vdash \varphi \quad \Delta \vdash \psi}{\Gamma \cup (\Delta \setminus \{\varphi\}) \vdash \psi} \text{proveHyp} \right| = \text{ProveHyp}|x||y||D_1|(\lambda x : ||\psi||.|D_2|), \text{ where } D_1 \text{ is the proof of } \varphi \text{ and } D_2 \text{ is the proof of } \psi.$$

Sym, *Trans* and *ProveHyp* have types as follows:

$$\text{Sym} : \Pi \alpha : \text{type}. \Pi x, y : \text{term } \alpha. \text{proof}(eq\ \text{bool}\ xy) \rightarrow \text{proof}(eq\ \text{bool}\ yx)$$

$$\text{Trans} : \Pi \alpha : \text{type}. \Pi x, y, z : \text{term } \alpha. \text{proof}(eq\ \alpha\ xy) \rightarrow \text{proof}(eq\ \alpha\ yz) \rightarrow \text{proof}(eq\ \alpha\ xz)$$

$$\text{ProveHyp} : \Pi x, y : \text{term}\ \text{bool}. \text{proof}\ x \rightarrow (\text{proof}\ x \rightarrow \text{proof}\ y) \rightarrow \text{proof}\ y$$

5 Evaluation and Benchmarks

ProofCloud includes also the proof checking results for all packages of OpenTheory. The standard library of OpenTheory grouped theorems into packages, including theorems of booleans, sets, lists, etc. The standard library (the base package, including 11 subpackages) was first verified in this project, followed by all the packages in the OpenTheory repository. For the first time, Holide and Dedukti successfully translated and checked all packages in OpenTheory. Table 3 illustrates the size of OpenTheory proof article files and the time taken for translation. Table 4 represents the size of translated files and the time taken for proof checking by Dedukti. We name the translators as Holide 1 and Holide 2 respectively corresponding to OpenTheory version 5 and 6 respectively in Table 3 and Table 4. Both article files and Dedukti files are compressed by *gzip* to reduce the effect of syntax formatting and whitespace. These benchmarks were generated on a 64-bit Intel Core i5-4590 CPU @3.30GHz \times 4 PC with 3.8GB RAM. However, there is little difference in terms of the size of article files and the efficiency between OpenTheory 5 and 6 for proof checking. The size of proof articles were reduced by around 7% while the proof checking time was reduced by around 5%. Figure 4 gives an example of the proof checking page of the stream package.

Package	Holide 1		Holide 2	
	Size (KB)	Time (s)	Size (KB)	Time (s)
base	1,436	19.35	1,194	19.42
cl	313	5.77	313	5.56
empty	0	0.20	0	0.00
gfp	136	1.42	112	1.35
lazy-list	1,390	31.43	1,391	31.78
modular	45	1.13	37	0.37
natural-bits	162	1.43	132	1.39
natural-divides	193	2.10	157	1.94
natural-fibonacci	130	1.31	108	1.24
natural-prime	140	1.46	116	1.34
parser	240	3.22	204	3.15
probability	26	0.30	23	0.23
stream	75	0.75	63	0.73
word10	86	0.76	71	0.62
word12	88	0.79	72	0.75
word16	131	1.60	107	0.77
word5	77	0.70	64	1.56
Total	4,668	73.73	4,377	72.21

Table 3: Size of Article Files and Translation Time

Package	Dedukti (Holide 1)		Dedukti (Holide 2)	
	Size (KB)	Time (s)	Size (KB)	Time (s)
base	4,681	10.63	4,440	9.74
cl	1,219	2.42	1,219	2.46
empty	0	0.00	0	0.00
gfp	400	0.73	375	0.65
lazy-list	5,718	13.31	5,717	13.11
modular	120	0.19	111	0.17
natural-bits	452	0.74	419	0.68
natural-divides	599	1.11	566	0.99
natural-fibonacci	378	0.67	354	0.60
natural-prime	408	0.72	388	0.65
parser	802	1.87	776	1.69
probability	72	0.12	69	0.11
stream	221	0.41	211	0.38
word10	234	0.38	216	0.29
word12	239	0.40	220	0.35
word16	396	0.80	364	0.36
word5	207	0.33	192	0.72
Total	16,146	34.83	15,637	32.95

Table 4: Size of Dedukti Files and Proof Checking Time

Figure 4: A Proof Checking Page of ProofCloud

Entry	Value
Proof Checking Engineer	Robert White
Time for verification	0.38(s)
Time for translation (if any)	0.73(s)
Software	Holide, Dedukti
Specification	64-bit with Intel @ Core i5-4590 CPU @ 3.30GHz * 4 and 3.8G memory on Ubuntu 15.04 running Ocaml 4.01 (and Camp5 6.12)

[Back to package page](#)

6 Conclusion

We have introduced ProofCloud and explained the implementation. ProofCloud is a customised search engine providing retrieval service for mathematicians and computer scientists using OpenTheory and reasoners in the HOL family. While OpenTheory packs proofs up, ProofCloud unpacks them and displays the proofs on webpages. It also help promoting OpenTheory and improve the usability of it. ProofCloud also presents proof checking results. The previous version of Holide can only translate the standard library of OpenTheory [1]. For the first time, all OpenTheory packages were translated by Holide and passed proof checking. This also provides evidence that OpenTheory is a reliable platform for higher order proofs and has validated the updates of Holide. However, as we have seen, there is little impact on the size of article files and efficiency of proof checking. Future work includes adding the remaining packages of OpenTheory to ProofCloud. Most recent updates of OpenTheory include also the names of proofs in packages. This would benefit the usability of ProofCloud.

7 Acknowledgement

The author was supported by MPRI-INRIA scholarship. During this project, the author received kind help from Dr. Gilles Dowek, Dr. Ali Assaf, Dr. Joe Hurd, Mr. Frédéric Gilbert and Mr. Nigel Sham and Mr. Dianlin Shen on the understanding and implementation of Holide, OpenTheory and ProofCloud.

References

- [1] Ali Assaf & Guillaume Burel (2015): *Translating HOL to Dedukti*. In: *Proceedings Fourth Workshop on Proof eXchange for Theorem Proving, PxTP 2015, Berlin, Germany, August 2-3, 2015.*, pp. 74–88.
- [2] Ali Assaf & Raphaël Cauderlier (2015): *Mixing HOL and Coq in Dedukti (Extended Abstract)*. In: *Proceedings Fourth Workshop on Proof eXchange for Theorem Proving, PxTP 2015, Berlin, Germany, August 2-3, 2015.*, pp. 89–96.
- [3] Denis Cousineau & Gilles Dowek (2007): *Embedding Pure Type Systems in the Lambda-Pi-Calculus Modulo*. In: *Typed Lambda Calculi and Applications, 8th International Conference, TLCA 2007, Paris, France, June 26-28, 2007, Proceedings*, pp. 102–117.
- [4] Thomas C Hales, John Harrison, Sean McLaughlin, Tobias Nipkow, Steven Obua & Roland Zumkeller (2011): *A Revision of the Proof of the Kepler Conjecture*. In: *The Kepler Conjecture*, Springer, pp. 341–376.
- [5] John Harrison (2009): *HOL Light: An Overview*. In: *Theorem Proving in Higher Order Logics, 22nd International Conference, TPHOLs 2009, Munich, Germany, August 17-20, 2009. Proceedings*, pp. 60–66.
- [6] Joe Hurd (2011): *The OpenTheory Standard Theory Library*. In: *NASA Formal Methods - Third International Symposium, NFM 2011, Pasadena, CA, USA, April 18-20, 2011. Proceedings*, pp. 177–191.
- [7] Cezary Kaliszyk & Alexander Krauss (2013): *Scalable LCF-Style Proof Translation*. In: *Interactive Theorem Proving - 4th International Conference, ITP 2013, Rennes, France, July 22-26, 2013. Proceedings*, pp. 51–66.
- [8] Marcel Oliveira, Ana Cavalcanti & Jim Woodcock (2006): *Unifying Theories in ProofPower-Z*, pp. 123–140. Springer.
- [9] Ronan Saillard (2013): *Dedukti: a universal proof checker*. In: *Foundation of Mathematics for Computer-Aided Formalization Workshop, January 9-11 2013, Padova, Italy*.
- [10] Konrad Slind & Michael Norrish (2008): *A Brief Overview of HOL4*. In: *Theorem Proving in Higher Order Logics, 21st International Conference, TPHOLs 2008, Montreal, Canada, August 18-21, 2008. Proceedings*, pp. 28–32.

A The Specification of ProofCloud

The following attributes are included in the webpages of each package:

- Package name
- Author of package
- Subpackages
- Date retrieved
- Total number of proofs
- Number of constructive proofs
- Number of classical proofs
- Percentage of constructive proofs
- Size of constructive proofs on average
- Size of classical proofs on average
- List of proofs (names and conclusions)
- Comments

For each package, there is also a page for verification (proof checking) information with the following entries:

- Software engineer for verification
- Software for verification
- Translation time
- Verification time
- PC Specification
- Comments

Each proof has its own page for structural, statistical and proof checking results with the attributes as follows:

- Theorem name
- Theorem conclusion
- Packagename
- Constructive proof (or not)
- Axioms
- Constructive lemmas (if any)
- Classical lemmas (if any)
- Package
- Comments